

LEARNING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM FOR CITI GLOBAL COLLEGE - CABUYAO CAMPUS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11393580>

ABSTRACT

This study delved into the existing educational processes and challenges faced by Citi Global College - Cabuyao Campus, with a focus on instructional delivery, student engagement, communication, and parental involvement. Through a descriptive-developmental research design utilizing both quantitative and qualitative methodologies, the study assessed the then-current state of affairs and identified obstacles hindering seamless interaction between educators, students, and parents. Findings revealed opportunities for improvement, particularly in enhancing parental engagement despite work-related constraints. The study suggested that implementing a Learning Management System (LMS) could provide an avenue for addressing these challenges by offering flexible access to educational resources and facilitating communication between educators and parents. Recommendations centered around strategies to augment instructional delivery, improve communication channels, and foster greater parental involvement within the existing framework. This research contributed to a deeper understanding of the educational dynamics at CGC - Cabuyao Campus and offered insights into potential avenues for enhancing student success and academic outcomes.

Keywords: *Learning Management System, Parents, Students, Information System, Education Technology, Record Management System*

INTRODUCTION

Nature and Scope of the Problem Investigated

This study delved into the existing educational processes and challenges faced by Citi Global College - Cabuyao Campus, with a focus on instructional delivery, student engagement, communication, and parental involvement. Through a descriptive-developmental research design utilizing both quantitative and qualitative methodologies, the study assessed the then-current state of affairs and identified obstacles hindering seamless interaction between educators, students, and parents. Findings revealed opportunities for improvement, particularly in enhancing parental engagement despite work-related constraints. The study suggested that implementing a Learning Management System (LMS) could provide an avenue for addressing these challenges by offering flexible access to educational resources and facilitating communication between educators and parents. Recommendations centered around strategies to augment instructional delivery, improve communication channels, and foster greater parental involvement within the existing framework. This research contributed to a deeper understanding of the educational dynamics at CGC - Cabuyao Campus and offered insights into potential avenues for enhancing student success and academic outcomes.

Research Objectives

1. Identify the existing processes at CGC - Cabuyao Campus in terms of learning modalities, particularly with: Instructional Delivery, Students academic performance and engagement, communication and parental monitoring
2. Determine the obstacles that hinder seamless interaction between educators, students, and parents in the existing learning modalities, communication methods, and parental monitoring procedures?
3. Assess the current system in terms of the ISO Software Characteristics.

Research Framework

The following section provided an overview of the conceptual framework that underpinned the research study on the "Learning Management System for Citi Global College - Cabuyao Campus." The conceptual framework functioned as a logical framework, offering a systematic perspective through which the fundamental elements and connections of the subject were thoroughly analyzed. The framework, at its essence, illustrated the complex interplay of inputs, processes, and outputs, providing a systematic approach for comprehending the difficulties within the current educational environment and imagining the revolutionary capacity of the suggested Learning Management System.

Figure 1: Research Framework

Research Significance

This research holds paramount significance for various stakeholders involved in the educational ecosystem: students, parents, and faculties. The researchers have stated the following significance that led to the main goal of the research: to add or contribute to the body of knowledge.

Scope and Limitation

This study was designed to investigate the challenges and limitations associated with the current learning modalities, communication methods, and parental monitoring procedures implemented at Citi Global College - Cabuyao Campus during the 2023 to 2024 academic year. The participants encompassed vital stakeholders within the educational community, including the senior high school principal, registrar, faculty members, students, and parents, ensuring a comprehensive representation. The research adopted a descriptive-quantitative method, employing statistical tools to analyze identified challenges systematically.

Various data-gathering tools, such as a survey questionnaire and interviews, collected information about the present educational process. A survey questionnaire administered to senior high school instructors provided quantitative insights, while an independent interview with the senior high school principal and registrar offered

qualitative perspectives. An online survey questionnaire was conducted to capture diverse views from senior high school students and parents. To ensure a representative sample, the study integrated Slovin's Formula, a non-probability sampling technique, specifically purposive sampling. The application of this technique was rooted in the distinctive characteristics of the senior high school community. The objective was to capture diversity, ensuring each subgroup's adequate representation in the sample. However, it was essential to acknowledge the study's limitations, including its focus solely on Citi Global College - Cabuyao Campus, limiting generalizability, and potential biases arising from the qualitative nature of interviews.

Review of Pertinent Literature

One of the principal objectives of a Learning Management System (LMS) is to enhance engagement, academic achievement, and interaction within the digital learning environment. The study by Avcı and Ergün (2022) investigated the impact of online students' LMS activities on their level of engagement, information literacy, and academic achievement. The results of their study revealed that the extent of participation in LMS may significantly impact students' academic achievement and engagement. However, it was not found to have a similar effect on students' information literacy. The diligent observation of student involvement levels can assist educators in identifying the specific requirements of students and providing appropriate learning support. It may be argued that high levels of student participation boost students' engagement in online courses. Therefore, it is possible to prevent learning issues in online learning settings. The results of the findings extend to students' online learning processes and instructional designs, which significantly impact students' achievements in online learning environments.

The study by Ricker, G., Belenky, D., and Koziarski, M. (2021) contributes to the existing body of knowledge by comprehensively examining the significance of parental engagement in LMS as a crucial factor in determining student achievement. This study emphasizes the influence of parental involvement on students' academic performance, specifically within grade bands where there is known variation in parental involvement. After accounting for variables recognized to influence educational achievements, it was observed that parental engagement, as assessed by the frequency of logins to the LMS, exhibited a modest, nevertheless favorable effect on students' academic performance throughout primary, intermediate, and secondary schooling levels. The findings indicate that parental participation holds equal, if not greater, significance in virtual schools than traditional educational environments.

Lastly, in the research of Washington, G. Y. (2019), students are used to having access to information 24/7, and the lines between online, blended, and in-person learning are blurring a bit. Although students might need help delivering instruction online, students like to have online access to their course materials, assignments, and grades. Being able to submit an assignment electronically is convenient, and students find comfort in seeing confirmation of their submission, along with the subsequent grade and feedback. In addition, the LMS can serve as a great spot to make sure that students are aware of and have quick access to any services that might be of assistance to them during the learning process (e.g., library, technical assistance, tutoring, scheduling office hours,

etc.). Making the most of the institution's LMS can help meet the shifting expectations of today's learners and create a more engaging and accessible learning environment for all students.

The use of personalization and adaptive learning has been increasingly prominent in the development of contemporary LMS. The research studied by Tadlaoui, M. A., and Khaldi, M. (2019) focused on investigating the aspects of personalization and cooperation within the context of adaptive E-Learning. The results of their study revealed that adaptive learning effectively enables learners to advance independently and at their preferred speed while also providing teachers with a comprehensive understanding of both the collective and individual success of students inside their classroom. In conjunction with this comprehensive analysis, adaptive learning technologies enable educators to monitor the progress of individual students closely. Students possess the capacity to monitor their development, while instructors are allowed to provide comprehensive and tailored explanations. For those experiencing challenges in their learning process, this technology has the benefit of mitigating their sense of isolation, which is a significant factor contributing to feelings of frustration and lack of success. In a platform specifically designed for adaptive learning, it is feasible to foster a sense of collaboration among users. The utilization of this program has demonstrated significant efficacy in fostering a sense of unity and coherence among students, both inside the confines of the classroom and beyond.

Exploring the flip side, Berry, Emily J (2019) investigates the viewpoints of parents and educators about family involvement activities and the obstacles that contribute to decreased participation rates. The study examines the viewpoints of families with children in pre-kindergarten regarding the significance of parental engagement in school-related activities. These activities encompass a range of events and initiatives, such as class celebrations, family activity nights, parent training/workshops, volunteering in the classroom, and participating in pre-k parent organizations. Parents provide accounts of the obstacles impeding their ability to participate in school-related events. Other elements, like the time of day, season, and external incentives, are also investigated. A series of interviews were conducted with educators to understand parental involvement in school activities comprehensively. These interviews aimed to gather educators' insights and perspectives regarding parents' role in school activities. The research reveals that job schedules represent the primary obstacles encountered by parents.

This study examines the incorporation of constructivist pedagogies within LMS. In this study, Castro, S. (2018) emphasizes the examination of the incorporation of LMS inside non-traditional educational settings that actively employ technology as a teaching tool. This study thoroughly examines the sustainability of a constructivist learning model by utilizing three learning technology tools made available to students through a LMS. By conducting a comprehensive analysis of multiple research studies on students' knowledge construction within a LMS, it can be deduced with precision that, under the guidance of a suitably trained facilitator within an appropriate instructional setting, students have the potential to cultivate learning outcomes aligned with constructivist principles through the utilization of discussion boards, weblogs, and assessments. The emerging connection between constructivism and LMS technology and the increasing connectivity of educational institutions presents significant potential benefits for a broader

range of students to engage in knowledge construction through novel and inventive means.

Expanding upon the notion of integrating conventional and digital forms of education, Bervell, B., Nyagorme, P., & Arkorful, V. (2020) investigated the efficacy of the flex model of blended learning in facilitating the enhancement of students' academic performance, self-directed learning abilities, and attitudes towards learning. A quasi-experimental study examined and compared the academic accomplishment, self-study skills, and learning attitudes of students in the control group who were exposed to traditional instructional methods with those of students in the experimental group who were exposed to the blended learning model. The research findings have substantiated that implementing blended learning has a beneficial effect on student's academic performance in the experimental group compared to the control group. This conclusion is supported by the results obtained from the independent t-test analysis conducted on both groups during the post-test phase. Furthermore, it was observed and determined through student opinion surveys that blended learning positively impacted student engagement with teachers, leading to enhanced academic performance, self-directed learning skills, and positive attitudes toward learning.

The sudden and unprecedented transformation in the education landscape, catalyzed by the COVID-19 pandemic, presented both challenges and opportunities, as illuminated by Idris, Zulkipli, Abdul-Mumin, Ahmad, Mitha, Rahman, and Naing (2021)—opportunities such as accessibility, opportunities for life-long-learning, improved quality and cost-effectiveness of educational resources. Challenges are the students facing increased anxiety during the pandemic, which may lead to decreased motivation towards studying. This can be correlated with increased concerns about academic, social, and economic well-being. College students can struggle with loneliness and isolation not only because of disconnections from friends but also because the abrupt disruption of the semester can cause cessation in their research projects and internships, leading to uncertainty in graduation and job market availability. Findings are essential to provide evidence for online pedagogical benefits and can promote the enhancement and adaptation of digital technology in education. The study promotes addressing the university community's physical and mental health issues by providing emotional and mental health support and appropriate programs. Thus, using an LMS is a safer approach to avoiding the community spread of COVID-19 without face-to-face interaction.

The pandemic has led to the shutdown of educational institutions around the world. Over 1.2 billion students are out of school globally. As a result of COVID-19, the education sector is facing a significant impact on universities, forcing their teaching to shift to e-learning and mixed-learning modes. During the current emergency, the LMS has been a vital resource for virtually all higher education institutions and a driving force in online learning, as reported by Arshad, M., Almufarreh, A., Norman, K. M., & Saeed, M. N. (2020). The research study explores the academic semester activities of Blackboard among the faculty members of the Faculty of Arts and Humanities of Jazan University in the middle of the COVID-19 pandemic. The results highlighted the space for teachers to assess the right Blackboard tools that are ideally suited to improving the students' success to achieve the learning outcomes they expect. The findings indicated that most faculty use Blackboard to promote their courses daily and 2-3 per week. The faculty also

uses the LMS's primary resources, including content sharing (course notes, lesson videos, PPT presentations, etc.), electronic evaluations, quizzes, assignments, and uploading grades. It is also recommended that the results of this study be shared with other higher learning institutions within and outside the country to motivate them to adopt learning management systems such as Blackboard Learn, which would support them by developing methods of pedagogy, educational outcomes in this dynamic market to build a strategic edge.

In response to the emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic, many educational institutions, including schools and universities, have implemented online learning platforms as a preventive measure to mitigate the transmission of the virus. Nevertheless, the authors' haste to use digital learning platforms resulted in an inadequate consideration of security concerns. Regrettably, the digital systems employed for online courses possess vulnerabilities that render them susceptible to unauthorized access by malicious actors. Moreover, there has been a notable rise in cyberattacks following the emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic. Hence, it is imperative to delineate the security concerns associated with digital learning environments in order to identify and implement effective measures that safeguard the well-being of both students and educators. The article by Djeki, E., Degila, J., Bondiombouy, C., and Alhassan, M. H. (2021) examines the subject of vulnerabilities and cyberattacks and their consequences on digital learning environments. The researchers employed the categorization of prevalent web application vulnerabilities as outlined by the Open Web Application Security Project (OWASP) and Common Weakness Enumeration (CWE). In addition to the technical risks, the article also emphasizes the presence of management and user operational risks stemming from human errors and lack of knowledge. In addition, a comparison study was conducted by researchers to analyze the vulnerabilities present in the most widely utilized LMS and video conferencing technologies. The study's findings indicate that Moodle exhibits the worst susceptibility to attacks, while Blackboard has the most significant level of security among LMSs. Furthermore, Zoom emerges as the best safe option among video conferencing tools.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-developmental research design to systematically examine the challenges and limitations associated with the current learning modalities, communication methods, and parental monitoring procedures at Citi Global College - Cabuyao Campus. Descriptive research aims to provide a detailed account of the prevailing conditions and characteristics within a specific context. In this study, this approach enabled a nuanced exploration of the educational landscape, allowing for the identification and analysis of the multifaceted challenges faced by the senior high school community. The descriptive design aligned to offer a comprehensive overview of the existing conditions and practices, setting the foundation for thoroughly examining the identified issues.

The chosen research type for this study was quantitative research, which involved collecting and analyzing numerical data to draw conclusions and identify patterns. Quantitative research was apt for this investigation because it provided statistically significant insights into the frequency and magnitude of challenges within the senior high school community at Citi Global College - Cabuyao Campus. Researchers employed surveys, questionnaires, and statistical tools to quantify the extent of challenges and obtain objective data, allowing for a rigorous and structured analysis. This research type ensured that the findings were not merely anecdotal but were grounded in empirical evidence, contributing to the robustness and reliability of the study.

Research Locale

The research was conducted at CITI Global College - Cabuyao Campus. The selection of the previous choice was based on many factors, including its zoning classification, the implementation of procedures throughout the campus, and the information technology index. The research included many data collection methods, including survey questionnaires and interviews, and was done at the respondents' convenience.

Population and Sampling Design

For this study, the researchers employed non-probability sampling and purposive sampling. Non-probability sampling is a method in which participants are not chosen randomly or with an equal chance of being chosen. Using a non-probability sampling technique called purposive sampling, the researchers chooses volunteers based on particular qualities or attributes relevant to the study.

Research Instrument

In this study, the researchers used questionnaires and interviews as a way of data collection. The questionnaire surveyed the teachers, students, and parents, while the interviews were used for the registrar and the principal. The study employed total enumeration for the principal, registrar, and senior high school instructors. This purposive sampling technique involved examining the entire population possessing specific characteristics. The total population for these roles was 27.

In contrast, for senior high school students and parents, purposive sampling was applied to limit the sample size to 50 for each group, thereby streamlining the research focus. Selecting senior high school students, instructors, parents, registrar, and principal as the target populations was crucial for a holistic understanding of the educational landscape. Students offered insights into their experiences and perceptions, instructors contributed as facilitators of learning, parents provided external support perspectives, and administrative figures like the registrar and principal offered insights into institutional operations. The use of non-probability sampling techniques guaranteed that the characteristics of each subgroup were proportionately represented. This approach strengthened the study's capacity to generalize findings to the broader senior high school community. The research aimed to enrich its exploration by including diverse

perspectives and providing a comprehensive and well-rounded understanding of challenges and limitations at Citi Global College - Cabuyao Campus.

Data Gathering Procedure

The statistical data analysis phase adopted a focused and nuanced methodology to extract valuable insights from the study dataset. The researchers employed the weighted mean as a statistical measure to determine the central tendency of participants' responses, providing a succinct depiction of the center value of the data. While employing the weighted mean, Microsoft Excel, and Google Forms for the survey questionnaire analysis, a parallel approach was applied to the qualitative data gathered through face-to-face interviews and later transcribed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Objective 1. The existing processes of CGC - Cabuyao Campus in terms of learning modalities. The researchers utilized the five-point Likert scale to calculate and interpret the data obtained from disseminated questionnaires, where a satisfaction scale of Very Satisfied, Satisfied, Neither satisfied or dissatisfied, Dissatisfied, and Very Dissatisfied is applied. The summary of responses and their corresponding verbal interpretation (VI) per weighted mean (WM) is shown in the tables below.

Table 1. The existing processes at CGC - Cabuyao Campus in terms of learning modalities.

Statements	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Instructional Delivery	4.56	Satisfied
2. Students' academic performance and engagement	4.54	Satisfied
3. Communication	4.54	Satisfied
4. Parental Monitoring	4.41	Satisfied
Overall Weighted Mean	4.54	Satisfied

With an overall WM and satisfaction level of 4.54, indicating satisfactory, the findings in Table 1 reveal the satisfaction in existing processes of CGC - Cabuyao Campus in terms of learning modalities. Respondents satisfied with the statement

regarding instructional delivery (WM = 4.56), students' academic performance and engagement (WM = 1.71), communication (WM = 4.54), and the parental monitoring denoted with a weighted mean of (WM = 4.41).

Objective 2. The obstacles that hinder seamless interaction between educators, students, and parents in the existing learning modalities, communication methods, and parental monitoring procedures. The study investigated obstacles hindering seamless interaction among educators, students, and parents within existing learning modalities and communication methods. It involved interviews with administrative figures from Citi Global College - Cabuyao Campus. The Registrar emphasized the importance of leveraging Learning Management Systems (LMS) to support student engagement and parental involvement. Challenges included parental decision-making in education, parental monitoring, and balancing work commitments with involvement in children's education. The Principal highlighted the flexibility of face-to-face and distance learning modalities, emphasizing the need for effective communication channels like group chats. Challenges included students' access to online resources and the importance of LMS during challenging times like the COVID-19 pandemic. Recommendations included increasing parent-teacher conferences and implementing dedicated LMS platforms tailored to students' needs. Both perspectives underscored the critical role of technology in enhancing communication and engagement within educational settings.

Objective 3. The Functionality, Reliability, and Efficiency of the Current System. The researchers utilized the five-point Likert scale to calculate and interpret the data obtained from disseminated questionnaires, where a quality scale of Very Good, Good, Acceptable, Poor, and Very Poor is applied. The summary of responses and their corresponding verbal interpretation (VI) per weighted mean (WM) is shown in the tables below.

Table 2. Students evaluation in the current system Functionality, Reliability, and Efficiency.

Statements	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Functionality	3.31	Acceptable
2. Reliability	3.50	Acceptable
3. Efficiency	3.47	Acceptable
Overall Weighted Mean	3.43	Acceptable

With an overall WM and quality level of 3.43, indicating acceptable, the findings in Table 2 reveal the students evaluation in the current system functionality, reliability, and efficiency. Respondents considered the statement acceptable regarding functionality (WM = 3.31), reliability (WM = 3.50), and efficiency denoted with a weighted mean of (WM = 3.47).

Table 3. Parents evaluation in the current system Functionality, Reliability, and Efficiency.

Statements	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Functionality	2.94	Poor
2. Reliability	2.96	Poor
3. Efficiency	2.60	Poor
Overall Weighted Mean	2.83	Poor

With an overall WM and quality level of 2.83, indicating poor, the findings in Table 3 reveal the parents evaluation in the current system functionality, reliability, and efficiency. Respondents considered the statement poor regarding functionality (WM = 2.94), reliability (WM = 2.96), and efficiency denoted with a weighted mean of (WM = 2.60).

Conclusions

Implementing the LMS offers a strategic resolution for addressing the difficulties related to the traditional learning method. Transitioning from the traditional to a digital approach offers significant benefits, especially to those forced to use distance learning. Through the utilization of technology, the campus can implement the system for ease of use.

The Senior High School (SHS) students of Citi Global College - Cabuyao Campus stand to be the primary beneficiaries of this research. Through improved communication channels and real-time access to academic resources, students can navigate their educational journey with greater autonomy, fostering a sense of responsibility and self-efficacy.

Educators at Citi Global College will find this research instrumental in reshaping their teaching methodologies. The proposed LMS equips faculty members with tools to enhance instructional delivery, streamline assessments, and provide timely feedback. By

leveraging technology to complement traditional teaching practices, faculty members can create a more dynamic and responsive learning environment, ultimately improving student outcomes. In order to facilitate a seamless transition to the proposed system, it is necessary to organize comprehensive teaching about the proposed system to ensure its ease of use and functionality.

Parents play a crucial role in a student's academic success, and this research recognizes and addresses their concerns. The proposed LMS actively involves parents in their children's education by offering real-time access to grades, performance metrics, and direct communication with professors. This heightened parental engagement fosters a collaborative approach to learning, where parents are empowered to support their children's academic endeavors more effectively.

Recommendations

Implementation of the LMS

The implementation of the LMS offers a strategic resolution for addressing the difficulties related to the traditional learning method. Transitioning from the traditional approach to a digital approach offers significant benefits, especially to those who are forced to use distance learning. Through the utilization of technology, the campus can implement the system for ease of use.

To the students

The Senior High School (SHS) students of Citi Global College - Cabuyao Campus stand to be the primary beneficiaries of this research. The proposed LMS offers a more interactive and personalized learning experience, facilitating better comprehension and engagement. Through improved communication channels and real-time access to academic resources, students can navigate their educational journey with greater autonomy, fostering a sense of responsibility and self-efficacy.

To the faculty

Educators at Citi Global College will find this research instrumental in reshaping their teaching methodologies. The proposed LMS equips faculty members with tools to enhance instructional delivery, streamline assessments, and provide timely feedback. By leveraging technology to complement traditional teaching practices, faculty members can create a more dynamic and responsive learning environment, ultimately improving student outcomes.

Training for faculties in using the proposed system

In order to facilitate a seamless transition to the proposed system, it is necessary to organize comprehensive teaching about the proposed system to ensure it is ease of use and functionality.

To the parents

Parents play a crucial role in a student's academic success, and this research recognizes and addresses their concerns. The proposed LMS actively involves parents in their children's education by offering real-time access to grades, performance metrics, and direct communication with professors. This heightened parental engagement fosters a collaborative approach to learning, where parents are empowered to support their children's academic endeavors more effectively.

To the future researchers

The findings of this study provide a rich resource for future researchers in the field of educational technology. As a reference, related study, and guide, this research offers a comprehensive understanding of the challenges and solutions in implementing an advanced LMS. Future researchers can build upon this study to further explore and refine technology integration in education, contributing to the ongoing evolution of pedagogical practices.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers complied with the basic standards of research ethics and also followed the Data Privacy Act in the collection and process of data gathered.

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